

SIMPLE LIMB INSTITUTE

AN AFFORDABLE PROSTHESIS FOR EVERYONE

Gerhardt Reichert, Leslie Speer

Hochschule für Gestaltung Schwäbisch Gmünd & San José State University

✉ gerhard.reichert@hfg-gmuend.de, leslie.speer@sjsu.edu

ABSTRACT

The Simple Limb Initiative¹ is a project and product delivery system built on the concept of affordability, co-design, cultural and emotional connection, scalability, and open source. Children throughout the world suffering from limb loss due to war, violence, or disease number in the hundreds of thousands². Their need for prosthetics that can grow with them, integrate them back into society, and provide a future of productivity is clear. The Simple Limb Institute website is a place where amputees, their representative, or a service organization can go to download plans for building a prosthesis (arm or leg) from locally sourced materials, using identified local organizations for fitting and rehab, for about the equivalent of US\$30. The selected prosthesis meets cultural and aesthetic norms for the region they live in. The project is in its infancy, with initial concepts developed and available for testing for Colombia, Afghanistan, and Cambodia. Future concepts for Colombia will be developed by May 2014 with plans to expand to several other countries over the next three years.

Connecting a user to the product they live with daily is dependent upon many things – but the ability for a product like a prosthesis to gain emotional integration into the life of a user is what can create a successful life story for a young child. Self-acceptance of their existence as an amputee, acceptance into a family, and integration into a community and a culture – all provide for a thriving life for a young child from their youth through to adulthood. This goal is at the heart of the Simple Limb Institute and through Design, we strive to achieve this goal with our collaborators and future customers.

KEYWORDS: *prosthetic, prosthesis, culture, aesthetic, emotion, co-design*

INTRODUCTION

This project began as a collaborative effort between two professors and their students from the Hochschule für Gestaltung Schwäbisch Gmünd³ in Germany and San José State University⁴ in California. The idea of a US\$30 prosthetic as a goal for a design project for Industrial Design students in their respective institutions drove the development and formation of this collaborative venture. Advanced level students in the respective undergraduate programs review each other's work, share research and data, and participate in WebEx critiques at the end of each phase of the project. The Simple Limb Institute is an ongoing receptacle for good and appropriate design solutions that meet the cultural, emotional, and functional needs of the amputee.

-
- 1 Simple Limb Initiative Website: <http://simplelimb.com/>
 - 2 Unicef: <http://www.unicef.org/graca/mines.htm>
 - 3 Hochschule für Gestaltung Schwäbisch Gmünd: <http://www.hfg-gmuend.de/>
 - 4 San José State University: www.sjsu.edu

PROJECT PHASES

The project for the course is set up with eight different phases, each one moving the student teams through various design activities with outcomes. A typical stage gate process, as described by Ulrich and Eppinger⁵, is followed and modified where required for this specific project. The phase descriptions and an image that describes the phases are below.

Phase 1 Analyze by reading Case Studies, review the ICRC and their manuals for production of prosthetics, review other manuals for prosthetics (Jaipur Foot, Jaipur Knee, Otto Bock, etc.), research the “place” (Cambodia, Colombia, Afghanistan), the people, the culture, and review ergonomic standards for children ages 5-15.

Phase 2 Reflect by thinking about what was learned from phase 1, get in contact with a local orthopedist to learn more about designing and building prosthetics, contact non-profit

-
- 5 Ulrich, K. and Eppinger, S., *Product Design and Development*, MacGraw-Hill Irwin, New York, 2011. Pgs. 12-22

organizations to start developing a “partnership” with someone in the country your team is assigned to, talk with amputees (lead users), and start sketching concepts.

Phase 3 Explore by sketching and building and testing out your ideas for functionality. Think about how you could integrate your solution in a business model that incorporates ideas of materials sourcing, building, fitting, training, and rehabilitation, all the steps required for successful prosthesis deployment.

Phase 4 Create testable artifacts for some of your more probable concepts further through prototypes, more detailed drawings, technical drawings, and renderings. Use yourself and your teammates as models to test the durability and functionality of the prototypes (use your testing apparatus to attach to yourselves).

Phase 5 Test your ideas! Get your prototype sent to an amputee or organization in your assigned country so that it can be tested and feedback given. Review the feedback, analyze it and use it to enhance/improve your design in the next phase.

Phase 6 Elaborate your final design ideas into the best appearance/functional prototype possible. This prototype should look like a final product and should also work well enough for someone to test it out. Use the intended materials for the final product and introduce cultural and aesthetic solutions that connect the product to the culture and the people.

Phase 7 Establish a public venue (website) for all the solutions. Organize into country pages and post your ideas for the business structure for fabrication and distribution and provide manuals for production and assembly in a visually cohesive website.

Phase 8 Care for the user/customer by providing a finalized website that includes information about producing, fitting, and training for the implementation of your prosthetics.

PROCESS

Throughout the project, students, amputees, occupational therapists, designers, and engineers worked collaboratively to develop solutions that met basic needs for a child amputee. Each team was assigned a country and the work to assess began.

Business Strategy

The goal is to have each team develop a different business strategy and unique solution that fits the country/culture they are designing for.

Collaboration

Teams are asked to locate a local organization in the country they are designing for. This organization could aid in fabrication or fitting or rehab with amputees. Here are examples found in the project last year⁶:

ICRC: International Council of the Red Cross/Red Crescent (global)

CIREC: Centro Integral de Rehabilitación de Colombia
Fundación Mi Sangre

6 ICRC (International Committee of the Red Cross): <http://www.icrc.org/eng/>; CIREC (Centro Integral de Rehabilitación de Colombia): <http://www.cirec.org/>; OMAR (Organization for Mine Clearance and Afghan Rehabilitation): <http://www.omar.org.af/english/>; AHDS (Afghan Health and Development Services): <http://www.ahds.org/>; IFRC (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent): <https://www.ifrc.org/>; Exceed (formerly known as The Cambodia Trust): <http://www.exceed-worldwide.org/>; USAID: <http://www.usaid.gov/>; Mahavir Kmina: <http://www.mahavir-kmina.org/>; Fundación Sin Manos: <http://www.sinmanos.org/amputado.html>.

Figure 1: Simple Limb Project Process

Simple Limb Initiative project team structure

	Design Strategy #1: made of 100% local materials, resources, labor	Design Strategy #2: made of mix of imported parts, locally made parts/labor	Design Strategy #3: made in China, India, or other hub	Design Strategy #4: other?
Team 1 (4)	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX
Team 2 (5)	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX
Team 3 (5)	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX
Team 4 (5)	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX
Team 5 (5)	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX

Figure 2: Simple Limb Team Structure and Business Model Structures

Fig 3: Some organizations discovered in the respective countries (Afghanistan, Cambodia, Colombia)

Fig. 4: Knee concept, foot concept, above-knee prosthetic concept.

OMAR: Organization for Mine Clearance and Afghan Rehabilitation

AHDS: Afghan Help and Development Services

RCRC: Rose Charities

The Cambodia Trust

USAID + VI (Veterans Internation)

Foundation Mahavir-Kmina

During the current academic year (SP14) students have successfully developed communication links with Mahavir Kmina and Sin Manos. Teams have been communicating with the organizations through the research and testing phases of their project and have successfully sent 2nd round functional prototypes to the organizations for evaluation of function and robustness. Feedback is currently being received and evaluated as they move towards finalizing their design.

Cultural/Emotional Connection Through Materials and Decoration

Teams investigated each culture, its people, its economy, its arts and industry, its material resources – paying specific attention to the arts and crafts of the regions. From their findings about local infrastructure, local organizations, and local resources and traditions, they were able to move into the concept development phase with an aesthetic direction identified.

Research methods were unique, as student teams were unable to visit any of these countries. San José State University is a deeply diverse institution, with an average of 10-15 different cultures sitting in any one classroom. Campus life includes many student organizations, many of which are set up for ethnically identified groups⁷. Additionally, the diversity of the faculty and administration provides opportunities to talk with recent immigrants and multi-generational households comprised of family members who visit their homeland frequently. Though not as good as doing research in-country, students were able to interview people from Afghanistan, Cambodia, and Colombia and get feedback on their projects from a culturally appropriate lens.

Concepts

Student teams moved through three (3) concept/prototype phases, each one with more and more refinement to the design. Some examples of testing, design inspiration (culture/aesthetic), and materials experiments follow. Initial concepts included concepts and first pass prototypes for knee joints, feet, hands, and different parts of the leg (pylon, socket, ankle). See some of the initial concepts below:

⁷ SJSU Student Clubs: <https://vpsaweb2.sjsu.edu/greenlight/pages/public/directory.php>

Results

Solutions for arm and leg prosthetics were presented at the end of the term. Both above elbow and below elbow prosthetics, along with above knee and below knee solutions, were presented by each team. Testing of the devices was done by construction of adult-scaled prototypes to test on team members. This allowed them to test for strength, movement, robustness, and usability. Teams did assessment of the prototypes, made adjustments to the design, and then right-sized the prototypes and associated instruction manuals for children ages 5-15. The reason children were chosen was two-fold. First, being able to get a child a prosthetic can allow them to continue on in school, receive a basic education, and successfully join the work world. Second, children's growth patterns provide a unique opportunity to design modular solutions that take into account how a child grows and how the prosthesis can change with the child, thereby reducing financial impact on the family with repeated prosthetic replacements.

The result of the project, the first time it was run, provided insights into successful approaches and gave the leadership team ideas on how to approach the project in the future. Although products were primitive, and had some flaws, there were a few successes. Each country had at least one successful concept to go forward to further testing. Multiples of those prototypes are being made to send out for testing now. Concurrently, the live website, with all the product plans are available for download, building and testing, with a provision that the customer provides feedback on the experience of building, fit, use, and learning curve for all aspects of the process.

The Simple Limb Initiative website is live and has generated some interest from other collaborators in the bio-medical programs at different institutions, along with the possibility of receipt of grant funds for further research and testing. The current semester project is focusing solely on Colombia, with projects being developed in both California and Germany, by students in the respective institutions.

Fig. 5: Results of first Simple Limb Initiative project.

FUTURE PLANS

The Simple Limb Initiative is in its infancy. It seeks to find interested collaborators for testing and deployment in the field. Only once the products have reached the children who are amputees, will the project be a success.

It is hoped that with the successful assistance of grant funding, the project leaders will be able to go to Colombia in the summer/fall of 2014 to engage in future research and establish long-term collaborations with local organizations (ICRC, CIREC, Mi Sangre, Sin Manos, and Mahavir Kmina).

Fig 6: Final functional prototypes/models.

Fig 7: Prototypes on model.

REFERENCES

- Simple Limb Initiative Website: <http://simplelimb.com/>
- Unicef: <http://www.unicef.org/graca/mines.htm>
- Hochschule für Gestaltung Schwäbisch Gmünd: <http://www.hfg-gmuend.de/>
- San José State University: www.sjsu.edu
- Ulrich, K. and Eppinger, S., Product Design and Development, McGraw-Hill Irwin, New York, 2011. Pgs. 12-22
- ICRC (International Committee of the Red Cross): <http://www.icrc.org/eng/>; CIREC (Centro Integral de Rehabilitación de Colombia): <http://www.cirec.org/>; OMAR (Organization for Mine Clearance and Afghan Rehabilitation): <http://www.omar.org.af/english/>; AHDS (Afghan Health and Development Services): <http://www.ahds.org/>; IFRC (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent): <https://www.ifrc.org/>; Exceed (formerly known as The Cambodia Trust): <http://www.exceed-worldwide.org/>; USAID: <http://www.usaid.gov/>; Mahavir Kmina: <http://www.mahavir-kmina.org/>; Fundación Sin Manos: <http://www.sinmanos.org/amputado.html>.
- SJSU Student Clubs: <https://vpsaweb2.sjsu.edu/greenlight/pages/public/directory.php>